

CO₂-SPICER - CO₂ Storage Pilot In a CarbonatE Reservoir

R7.6 Data set and report with results of reservoir containment monitoring

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1 INTRODUCTION

The reservoir characterization, geological modelling, assembling and history matching of the reservoir model and geomechanical evaluations (Nermoen, Shchipanov, Porzer, & Sancer, 2024) have provided background information for preparing reservoir containment monitoring plan as described below.

The reservoir contains gas cap above the oil zone and the brine saturated area below the oil zone is connected to a limited aquifer. No faults have been identified inside the main reservoir domain to be used for pilot CO₂ injection. Geomechanical evaluations have indicated possibility of opening natural fractures at 224 bar and induced fracturing 267 bar if CO₂ is injected at 15 C. These evaluations are however uncertain accounting for uncertainty with the in-situ stress state and impact of natural fractures (Nermoen, Shchipanov, Porzer, & Sancer, 2024). The ZA7 well (Fig. 1-1), recently recompleted (below the initial Water-Oil-Contact (WOC) and located horizontally outside the OWC for the current oil rim) and injecting water into the reservoir for many years, is chosen as candidate for CO₂ injection. A few wells are present nearby the well ZA7 (Fig. 1-1). The nearby well ZA9AH may be used for monitoring of planned pilot CO₂ injection in ZA7 well, understanding well communication and horizontal transmissibility of the natural fracture network in the ZA7 – ZA9AH inter-well area.

Fig. 1-1: Top-view depth map of the field with initially gas (red), oil (green) and water (blue) saturated areas with well trajectories. ZA7 injection well is marked with the circle.

2 WELL MONITORING DATA AVAILABLE

Well monitoring data accumulated by the field operator during more than twenty years of production history may be analysed to evaluate experience gained and capabilities of the well surveillance system in the context of the reservoir characterization and monitoring. Additional well monitoring dataset gained during the current project is also overviewed with highlighting potential areas of its application.

2.1 Historical data

Different well monitoring data are available for the production and injection wells drilled in the field. Many wells were tested after drilling as illustrated with an example of the well ZA7 data presented and analysed in the following sections. Permanent well monitoring with installation of permanent downhole gauges was also attempted. The most representative permanent well monitoring dataset is available for the horizontal production well ZA5H drilled in the central part of the field (Fig. 1-1). These data were used in this report to illustrate possible application and capabilities of time-lapse Pressure Transient Analysis (or time-lapse PTA, (Shchipanov, Berenblyum, & Kollbotn, 2014)) for reservoir characterization and well monitoring. This includes characterizing well drainage area and estimating well-reservoir parameters such as reservoir flow capacity and well skin and how these parameters vary over time. Fig.2-1 displays the PDG data at depth 2,484 m MD (at the bottom part of oil zone, while this horizontal well was drilled within the oil zone) for 2 years history since the beginning of well production, including a few flowing (production) and shut-in (pressure build-up) periods. In this period, the well was producing above the bubble-point pressure with minor water-cut after half a year of pure oil production. Two shut-in periods with pressure build-up (BU1 and 2) and one following production (PROD3) period were analysed using the Saphir software to estimate well and reservoir parameters and boundary conditions on the well drainage area.

Fig. 1-1: Three sequential shut-in (build-ups: BU1, 2 and 3) and one flowing (production: PROD3). Solid red line for pressure is result of simulation with the PTA-model.

The production and build-up responses represented in log-log scale in Fig. 2-2 indicate signature of no-flow boundary conditions on the well drainage area in the pressure derivatives, if flowing pressure responses are compared with shut-in responses. A fit-for-purpose analytical reservoir model was then used to estimate reservoir flow capacity, kh ,

by using the stabilized pressure derivative level between 1 and 10 hr. This model also reproduced the closed reservoir response recognized by an increasing derivative during production and decreasing derivative in the build-up periods at later times (i.e., after 10 hr).

Fig. 2-2: Pressure transient responses in the log-log scale for the build-up and production periods from Fig. 2-1. Solid lines with corresponding colours are simulation results with the PTA-model.

The well monitoring dataset presented above was gained in the beginning of oil production started from 2004, before gas breakthrough. This dataset enabled revealing boundary conditions of the well drainage area. Time-lapse PTA (Fig. 2-3) interpretations revealed significant reduction of the well pressure drop over time (and increasing well productivity). The observed effect was reproduced in the well-reservoir model, where the effective well length was increased from 40 (Build-Up #1, 2 and Production #3) to 160 m (Build-Up #3 and Production #4). Such effects are commonly observed for horizontal wells, where wells start to drain a segment near the well heel with extending this segment towards to the well toe. This may be considered as a possible explanation of the observed effect, although alternative explanations are also possible. As an alternative, improvement of flow capacity (clean-up) of the near wellbore area may be also considered and we were able to reproduce such effect in the reservoir model with applying reducing skin.

Fig. 2-3: Time-lapse pressure responses and their derivatives for three well shut-in (Build-Up #1, 2 and 3) and flowing (Production #3 and 4) periods of well ZA5H.

The permanent well monitoring example above confirmed capabilities and value of installing PDG in potential CO₂ injection wells, where time-lapse PTA interpretations may be potentially useful for monitoring changes in well-reservoir parameters, in particular, in the near-wellbore area, where CO₂ plume may be formed and dynamic effects such as natural fracture opening and induced fracturing may happen.

2.2 New observation data from ZA3 well

In the course of the project, a PDG was installed in the observation well ZA3 and pressure was monitored during two and a half months (Fig. 2-4). During this monitoring period, production operations were carried out in the nearby wells including start of production after well shut-in period and change in production rate. These events were reflected in the pressure measurements in the observation well (Fig. 2-4). The pressure variation range in this period was at the level of 0.1 bar, which is quite small compared to pressure drops during production or injection operations. It argues that it would be difficult to use pressure measurements in an active injection well to monitor nearby wells (e.g. wellbore leakage), since the pressure drops and noise from injection operations would be much higher than 0.1 bar as illustrated in the next sections. The ZA3 well monitoring data confirmed value of installing PDG in observation wells to monitor operations in nearby production or injection wells and may be recommended for a nearby production well to the CO₂ injection well during the pilot. Production from chosen nearby well should be stopped for the period of pilot CO₂ injection to transform this well into an observation one.

Fig. 2-4: Pressure monitoring data from the observation well ZA3 for the period of 21/07/2021 to 01/10/2021.

3 RESERVOIR CONTAINMENT MONITORING

3.1 Potential factors challenging CO₂ containment in the reservoir

The following risks for reservoir containment during pilot CO₂ injection and reservoir pressure build-up may be considered based on the studies (Nermoen, Shchipanov, Porzer, & Sancer, 2024) and (Ford, et al., 2023):

1. Opening of natural fractures governed by reservoir pressure build-up. This may be considered as a moderate risk associated with potential fracture growth towards the cap-rocks providing potential leakage pathways. Opening of natural fractures may also have a positive impact on effective permeability of the fractured reservoir increasing well injectivity. The geomechanical evaluations (Nermoen, Shchipanov, Porzer, & Sancer, 2024) suggested that the natural fractures to be opened at pressure above 224 bar.
2. Creating an induced fracture connected to the well ZA7, if injection pressure overcomes the fracturing pressure (estimated as 267 bar in (Nermoen, Shchipanov, Porzer, & Sancer, 2024)). This may be considered as a high risk for reservoir containment, since induced fracturing and uncontrolled fracture growth through cap-rocks may cause out-of-zone injection and intensive leakage out of the target formation.
3. Potential of wellbore leakages through abandoned wells is also present as extensively studied in (Ford, et al., 2023). Based on the observation well data described in the previous section, monitoring of leakage in a nearby well from pressure data in the active injection well (ZA7) does not look like a possible option. At the same time, using a nearby production well (e.g. ZA9AH) as an observation well for the pilot CO₂ injection monitoring may be a viable option to analyse ZA7 – ZA9AH interference and pressure build-up at a distance from the injection well.

Based on the points described above, this study is focused on monitoring of opening of natural fractures using PDG in injection well and step-rate testing or injection. Water injection SRT is first evaluated as an option to evaluate fracture opening pressure, while step-rate CO₂ injection is further studied to evaluate feasibility of fracture opening monitoring in the presence of growing CO₂ plume. Following the geomechanical evaluations (Nermoen, Shchipanov, Porzer, & Sancer, 2024), induced fracturing may be expected after opening of the natural fractures. Similar PTA-approach may be used for detection of the induced fracturing, but adaption of the approach for such a case is subject of further study.

3.2 Well monitoring system design

Based on the risks described above, the following design of well surveillance system and well monitoring equipment for the CO₂ injection well is suggested:

- A flow-meter to be installed permanently at the wellhead to monitor and collect CO₂ injection rate data in real time with minimum sampling rate of 5 seconds.

- Combined wellhead and downhole pressure and temperature (P&T) gauges to permanently installed in the well to collect measurements with same minimum frequency (5 seconds). The best location of the permanent downhole gauge (PDG) is as close as possible to the sand-face

The minimum requirements for the P&T gauges to be installed at wellhead and downhole of the well are listed in Tab. 3-1.

Tab. 3-1: Minimum requirements for P&T gauges

Gauge specification	Value
Pressure accuracy, bar	± 0.3
Pressure resolution, bar	0.001
Temperature accuracy, °C	± 0.5
Temperature resolution, °C	0.01

This well monitoring design (Fig. 3-1) enables:

- Monitoring of wellhead and downhole CO₂ injection rates, where the latter is calculated based on the surface rate and temperature and pressure downhole (from PDG measurements). The CO₂ injection rate at the reservoir conditions is crucial input data for the interpretation of pressure transient data.
- High frequency of pressure and rate measurements enables monitoring of dynamic process in the near wellbore area such as opening of natural fractures and creating of induced fractures. Here, high-frequency PDG data also allow for distinguishing the wellbore storage effects occurred at CO₂ injection and masking early time response in pressure transients.

Fig. 3-1: A schematics of CO₂ injection well with wellhead and downhole gauges installed. Modified from <https://co2geonet.com/>

3.3 Fit-for-purpose model for studying well monitoring capabilities

A fit-for-purpose reservoir model was assembled in the Saphir software based on basic geological data including the reservoir geometry, well location and average reservoir (such as porosity and pay-thickness at the well location, pore volume compressibility) and fluid (brine PVT) properties.

The main purposes for assembling and using the reservoir model are:

- Interpretation and matching the well testing results to estimate reservoir properties and boundary conditions in the well drainage area as far as may be evaluated from available pressure transient data.
- Designing and simulating well tests for detecting natural fracture opening.
- Evaluating feasibility of detecting and monitoring natural fracture opening for water and CO₂ injection.

Variation in reservoir depth, pay thickness, presence of remaining oil and gas in the reservoir as well as impact of pressure support from a limited aquifer connected from the East were neglected in the simulations, which is assumed to be reasonable assumptions accounting for the study purposes. The reservoir model and the well ZA7 completion schematics are illustrated in Fig. 3-2. The well has 112 m of open-hole connection to the reservoir of total thickness of 158 m providing limited entry well-reservoir connection (Bourdet, 2002).

Fig. 3-2: A reservoir segment model containing a vertical water injection well in focus (a) and the well completion schematics showing open-hole interval and initial water saturation profile (b).

A water injection well test was carried out after completing the well in 2004, where downhole pressure gauge was installed and provided 10-hour pressure measurements

during well shut-in (Fig. 3-3). Water was injected for 5.5 hours with two rate measurements, where the first hour of the injection the wellbore was filled in by the injected water with well injection at atmospheric pressure at the wellhead. Large changing wellbore storage was observed in combination with large well skin factor interpreted at the beginning of the shut-in period (Fig. 3-3). The large skin (providing additional pressure drop of 71 bar (Fig. 3-3-a) in comparison with 4 bar overall pressure drop ignoring the skin (Fig. 3-3-b)) seems to be related to the damage (clogging) of the near wellbore area with drilling mud, since it's far above a skin provided by the limited entry connection (Fig. 3-3-b).

Fig. 3-3: Pressure fall-off response and its Bourdet derivative from water injection test (crosses / dots) and matching the response with the segment reservoir model (Figure 6-a) with large (a) and zero (b) well skin – red and black lines. Flow regimes: identified in the real response derivative (a) and in the simulated response with zero skin (b).

Interpretation of the pressure fall-off response and its Bourdet derivative in the log-log scale allowed to separate four flow regimes (Fig. 3-3-a): (1) wellbore storage effect at early time (0-0.3 hr), (2) limited well entry response (0.3-0.7 hr), (3) radial flow regime (0.7-2 hr) and (4) boundary-dominated flow regime at the late time (2-10 hr). The last flow regime is governed by the closest no-flow reservoir boundaries to the West and South from the well (Fig. 3-2-a). It is assumed that the near wellbore area has been successfully cleaned-up during periodical water injection during twenty years. A zero-skin case was then simulated on with the same well-reservoir model to get base-line pressure transient response for the well (Fig. 3-3-b).

The geomechanical study (Nermoen, Shchipanov, Porzer, & Sancer, 2024) as resulted in the safe injection envelope showing fracture opening pressure for natural fractures, induced fracturing pressure and pressure at which fault reactivation may happen (Fig. 3-4-a). Fixing reservoir temperature at 15 °C (the minimum temperature of injected CO₂), the fracture opening and induced fracturing pressures may be evaluated as 224 and 267 bar correspondingly. An exponential increase of the effective reservoir permeability may be modelled in this range to model opening of natural fractures (Fig. 3-4-b). Such fracture modelling approach seems to be sufficient for the purposes of the feasibility study. Injection of water and CO₂ may be further simulated on the reservoir model matched to the well test results.

Fig. 3-4: Safe injection envelope from (Nermoen, Shchipanov, Porzer, & Sancer, 2024) indicating fracture opening and induced fracturing pressures at 224 and 267 bar for reservoir temperature of 15 °C (a) and pressure dependent multipliers for reservoir porosity and permeability (b). Two permeability multipliers: without and with natural fracture opening contributions. SRT range is the pressure build-up expected in the step rate test designs.

3.4 Well testing to study opening of natural fractures

The geomechanical evaluations (Nermoen, Shchipanov, Porzer, & Sancer, 2024) have reveal large uncertainties with in-situ stresses which made also uncertain the assessment of horizontal stresses governing opening and closure of the natural fracture networks during reservoir pressure build-up and drawdown. Such dynamic fracture behaviour may also be evaluated from dynamic data analysis presented above, although no reservoir permeability changes were revealed, probably due to narrow pressure range associated with the field data available. The geomechanical study (Nermoen, Shchipanov, Porzer, & Sancer, 2024) has however provided a prediction of potential opening of the natural fractures (Fig. 3-4-a) under the uncertainty described above and suggested a description of the pressure dependent fracture permeability (Fig. 3-4-a).

Step-rate testing (Shchipanov, Kollbotn, Prosvirnov, 2017) or step-rate injection may be used for detecting and monitoring of opening / closure of natural fractures under reservoir pressure changes if PDG is installed in the well monitored. A step-rate test with water injection is recommended in the well in focus (ZA7) before CO₂ pilot to reduce the uncertainties with the geomechanical parameters described above.

The scope and objectives of such step-rate well test may include:

- Since the well ZA7 was recently recompleted with wellbore cleaning and new tubing installed, the current well-reservoir parameters may be evaluated from the well test including reservoir flow capacity (permeability-thickness product), well skin and wellbore friction (from combined wellhead and downhole pressure measurements). Both pressure transients from injection and shut-in periods may be analysed for this purpose.
- Opening of natural fractures as predicted by the geomechanical evaluations may be studied from the step-rate test employing the approach suggested in

(Shchipanov, Kollbotn, & Prosvirnov, Step rate test as a way to understand well performance in fractured carbonates (SPE-185795), 2017).

Following these objectives, a step-rate test was designed based on the knowledge obtained and the well-reservoir model matched in the previous well test (from 2004) analysis described in the previous section (Fig. 3-3). Since the well was recompleted, zero skin model (Fig. 3-3-b) was used in combination with the pressure dependent reservoir permeability (Fig. 3-4-b). The zero skin assumption should be however verified prior such SRT, since the current well connection to the reservoir should be first evaluated. A single-rate short injection well test may be planned to evaluate current skin and reservoir flow capacity to allow for proper planning of the following well test in terms of injection volumes and facilities needed. The SRT design includes three injection steps (3-hour duration) with following measurement of pressure fall-off during the well shut-in (at least 9 hours). Two scenarios were simulated: without and with fracture opening at 224 bar (Fig. 3-5-a). Both analysis of the simulated SRT results in linear scale (Fig. 3-5-a) and log-log scale (Fig. 3-5-b), where pressure transient responses and their derivative to injection steps is analysed, provided clear indication of the fracture opening. This indication consists of much lower pressure drop and drifting-down of pressure and derivative at the third step, where fractures start to open.

Fig. 3-5: Step-rate-test simulated for water injection (a) and pressure transient responses and their derivatives for three steps of the test in log-log plot (b). Crosses in Fig. 3-5-b correspond to the 'Fracture closed' case, while lines with the same colour for the same steps to the 'Fracture opening' case.

The simulations have confirmed that SRT with water injection may serve as reliable tool for detection and studying fracture opening. This simulation study did not account for potential induced fracturing, since opening of natural fractures is expected as the first event happening at injection and pressure build-up. Studying this effect is therefore giving priority. At the same time, induced fracturing may also be detected with SRT, which may be a subject for further study of the reservoir in focus.

3.5 Well testing and injection monitoring during CO₂ injection

The SRT with water injection simulated in the previous section of the report may be extended to the case of CO₂ injection and used as the well control framework for further time-lapse monitoring of the well. The short steps with increasing rate in SRT may be

substituted with longer steps of combined increasing and decreasing rates in long-term time-lapse well monitoring.

Fig. 3-6-a illustrates simulation results for similar SRT to one simulated in the previous section for water injection and shown in Fig. 3-5-a, where the injectant is changed from water to CO₂. As in the water injection scenario above, two cases of pressure dependent fracture permeability are considered (Fig. 3-4): ‘Fracture closed’ and ‘Fracture opening’. Flooding the near wellbore area with CO₂ has an impact on the first injection step (Fig. 3-6-a), where the pressure derivative is significantly affected (Fig. 3-6-b). CO₂ plume in the near wellbore area is stabilized at the second step, providing similar pressure transient responses and derivatives for both fracture cases (transients and derivatives are coinciding in Fig. 3-6-b). In contrast to water injection responses (Fig. 3-5-b), presence of CO₂ plume in the near wellbore area is reflected by lower derivative at the early time (0.001-0.01 hr, Fig. 3-6-b). Fracture opening at the third step may clearly detected at the third step with the derivative shifting down for the whole duration of the response (Fig. 3-6-b).

Fig. 3-6: Similar SRT to one illustrated in Fig. 3-5 for CO₂ injection. Crosses in Fig. 3-6-b correspond to the ‘Fracture closed’ case, while lines with the same colour for the same steps to the ‘Fracture opening’ case.

The feasibility study has confirmed possibility of detecting fracture opening under CO₂ injection. At the same time, impact of growing CO₂ plume should first be observed in pressure transients to provide base-line for further successful fracture opening detection.

4 RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

The analysis and evaluation of available dynamic field data have shown that installation of permanent downhole gauge (PDG) in production wells is an effective option for permanent well and reservoir monitoring for the fractured formation in focus. Application of time-lapse PTA in combination with fit-for-purpose reservoir simulations (Shchipanov, Berenblyum, & Kollbotn, 2014) allowed for monitoring of well and reservoir parameters. Similar monitoring approach is suggested for the planned CO₂ pilot.

A design of well monitoring system was suggested for the CO₂ injection well including installation of permanent wellhead pressure and temperature gauges in combination with flow-meter at the wellhead. This will allow to monitor the wellbore and well performance as well as evaluate changes in the near wellbore area of the reservoir, which may challenge the reservoir containment of the injected CO₂.

A step-rate well test with water injection is suggested before the CO₂ pilot to study potential opening of natural fractures at injection and reduce the uncertainty with geomechanical parameters, e.g. to evaluate unknown parameters such as minimum horizontal stress.

The feasibility study of step-rate CO₂ injection confirmed that PTA of the step-responses may be used to:

- Evaluate CO₂ plume growth in the near wellbore area.
- Detect opening of natural fractures.

Similar approach may be further tested for detection of induced fracturing, which may happen after natural fracture opening as predicted by the geomechanical evaluations. This effect may be addressed in a future study.

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